

2,4-Dinitrophenoxides of zirconium(IV)

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Abstract : Complexes of composition $ZrCl_{4-n}(dnp)_n$ (where dnp is anion of 2,4-dinitrophenol i.e. $OC_6H_3(NO_2)_2-2,4$) have been synthesized by the reaction of zirconium tetrachloride with equimolar and bimolar amounts of 2,4-dinitrophenol (dnpH) in toluene under reflux and characterized by elemental analysis, conductivity measurements, infrared and proton NMR spectral studies. Thermal behaviour of these complexes has also been investigated and using TG data, thermodynamic parameters have been calculated. The reaction of the parent complexes with nitrogenous bases such as 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl results in the formation of simple addition compounds characterized by analytical and infrared spectral studies.

Keywords : Zirconium(IV), 2,4-dinitrophenol, thermal behaviour, Lewis acid character.

Introduction

Compared to the considerable effort to develop the chemistry of zirconium alkoxides and their derivatives to provide better precursors for the deposition of materials¹⁻⁵, very little attention seems to have been devoted towards the synthesis of closely related zirconium aryloxides⁶⁻¹⁰. The catalytic properties of chelating phenoxide complexes of titanium and zirconium in the polymerization of alkynes have been reported by Linden and coworkers¹¹. Phenolic ligands containing a second donor at *ortho* position are also known to exhibit a behaviour wherein coordination from both phenolic oxygen and donor atoms at *ortho* position occurs^{12,13}. In view of these interesting reports, in the present investigations, an attempt therefore has been made to synthesize some new aryloxides of zirconium(IV) using $ZrCl_4$ and 2,4-dinitrophenol and their potential as Lewis acids has been studied by undertaking their reactions with various nitrogenous bases.

Results and discussion

The reactions of zirconium tetrachloride with 2,4-dinitrophenol (dnpH) in toluene afforded the formation of compounds $ZrCl_3(dnp)$ and $ZrCl_2(dnp)_2$ according to the equation

These compounds are greenish yellow solids. The stoichiometric composition of the solids has been established by elemental analysis given in Table 1. They are insoluble in most of the common organic solvents, partially soluble in nitrobenzene and nitromethane and soluble in methanol. Molar conductance values of millimolar solutions of the compounds in nitrobenzene suggest them to be non-electrolytes.

The ¹H NMR spectral data of free 2,4-dinitrophenol display one sharp signal at δ 4.65 ppm assigned to the phenolic OH group and three distinct resonances due to aromatic protons at 9.1, 8.5 and 7.35 ppm. The latter three resonances have been attributed to two different kinds of protons viz. (i) (m) having two neighbouring NO₂ groups at 2- and 4-positions, (ii) (m') having one adjacent NO₂ group and third *ortho* to phenolic group respectively. In the proton NMR spectra of the complexes $ZrCl_3(dnp)$ and $ZrCl_2(dnp)_2$, signal due to phenolic OH group disappeared while those due to three kinds of aromatic protons (m, m', and o) appeared slightly downfield compared to pure 2,4-dinitrophenol. These shifts have been attributed to the delocalization of electron from the aromatic ring to zirconium resulting in the formation of bonding of the type ArO---Zr. A similar view point has been proposed earlier also in literature on tantalum penta phenoxides¹⁴.

In IR spectra, broad band observed in the region 3400-

Table 1. Analytical data of 2,4-dinitrophenoxides of zirconium(IV) and their addition compounds with nitrogenous bases

Compd.	Colour and physical state	Elemental analysis (%) :				Molar conductance in nitrobenzene ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Molecular weight in PhNO_2	
		Found (Calcd.)		Found (Calcd.)			Found	Calcd.
		Zr		Cl				
$\text{ZrCl}_3(\text{dnp})$	Greenish yellow solid	23.11	(23.95)	27.68	(28.02)	2.307	-	380
$\text{ZrCl}_2(\text{dnp})_2$	Greenish yellow solid	16.60	(17.23)	13.56	(13.45)	2.025	-	528
$\text{ZrCl}_3(\text{dnp})\cdot\text{phen}$	Orange solid	16.20	(16.25)	18.92	(19.01)	1.24	540	560
$\text{ZrCl}_2(\text{dnp})_2\cdot\text{phen}$	Orange solid	12.70	(12.85)	10.32	(10.02)	1.83	-	7.8
$\text{ZrCl}_3(\text{dnp})\cdot\text{bipy}$	Reddish brown solid	16.76	(16.98)	19.80	(19.87)	1.47	520	537
$\text{ZrCl}_2(\text{dnp})_2\cdot\text{bipy}$	Reddish brown solid	13.07	(13.30)	9.95	(10.38)	1.09	-	684

dnp = Anion of 2,4-dinitrophenol i.e. $^-\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{-2,4}$.

phen = 1,10-Phenanthroline, bipy = 2,2'-bipyridyl.

3300 cm^{-1} due to intramolecularly bonded OH group in free 2,4-dinitrophenol was found absent indicating the deprotonation of phenolic group on complexation. It has also been substantiated by an observation that there was immediate evolution of hydrogen chloride gas during the course of reaction of ZrCl_4 with 2,4-dinitrophenol. The most important band due to phenolic $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ mode observed at 1255 cm^{-1} in the phenol under study has remained almost unchanged in the complexes in contrast to a significant decrease in the frequency of this band reported in metal alkoxides and aryloxides^{15,16}. The observed trend of $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ mode on complexation may be attributed to weaker coordination of dinitrophenolic ligand perhaps due to ring conjugation. The occurrence of entirely new bands in the region $560\text{--}490 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (not present in the ligand) attributed to $\nu(\text{Zr}-\text{O})$ modes^{17,18} has suggested the coordination from oxygen of the phenol with zirconium. Apart from this, bands observed at ~ 1545 and 1342 cm^{-1} attributed to antisymmetric and symmetric vibrations respectively of NO_2 group in the free phenol have remained unaltered even on complexation suggesting non-coordination of the *ortho* NO_2 group through oxygen to the metal. Bands observed in the region $360\text{--}340 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been assigned to $\nu(\text{Zr}-\text{Cl})$ modes¹⁷. Based upon limited analytical, conductance, proton NMR and IR spectral studies, a tetrahedral environment has tentatively been proposed for the compounds of composition $\text{ZrCl}_3(\text{dnp})$ and $\text{ZrCl}_2(\text{dnp})_2$.

A careful examination of the thermograms of $\text{ZrCl}_3(\text{dnp})$ and $\text{ZrCl}_2(\text{dnp})_2$ (Fig. 1) indicate that they are stable upto 44.1 and 42.9 °C respectively and subse-

Fig. 1. TGA/DTA curves of $\text{ZrCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{-2,4})$ (—) and $\text{ZrCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2\text{-2,4}))_2$ (---).

quently decomposes in a single stage. The overall weight loss of 67.5% and 76.5% for the respective complexes has been found to account for the formation of ZrO_2 as the final residue. DTA curves have shown that the entire decomposition is a combination of both exothermic and endothermic processes. The higher value of activation energy (E^*) for $\text{ZrCl}_3(\text{dnp})$ ($22.937 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) compared to $\text{ZrCl}_2(\text{dnp})_2$ ($20.901 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$), calculated using Coats and Redfern eq. (19) suggests that former compound is more stable than the latter, which is further substantiated by the positive value of free energy of activation (G^*), 253.282 and $158.481 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ respectively for these complexes. Negative value of entropy of activation (S^*), -366.71 and $-354.62 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ for these respective complexes is indicative of slow but alike decomposition.

Reaction with nitrogenous bases :

The complexes $ZrCl_3(dnp)$ and $ZrCl_2(dnp)_2$ have shown considerable reactivity towards nitrogen bases such as 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) and 2,2'-bipyridyl (bipy). The addition compounds isolated (Table 1) are moisture sensitive but stable in dry atmosphere. Molar conductance values of millimolar solutions of these compounds in nitrobenzene are too low to be attributed to 1 : 1 electrolytes while molecular weight determination of some of these addition compounds in nitrobenzene, where the solubility indicate that they exist as monomers in this solvent. IR bands due to $\nu(C=C)$ and $(C=N)$ and C-H out-of-plane deformation modes of the free 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl have shifted towards higher spectral region by about $20-30\text{ cm}^{-1}$ upon adduct formation suggesting the coordination from both the nitrogen atoms of the ligand. This observation is in agreement with the previously reported metal halide complexes with these bases²⁰. The coordination of these bases to zirconium has further been substantiate by the appearance of entirely new bands in the $290-270\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region assigned to $\nu(Zr-N)$ modes²¹.

On the basis of the limited analytical, conductance, molecular weight determination and infrared spectral data, an octahedral structure has tentatively been assigned for these addition compounds. It has further been concluded that compounds of composition $ZrCl_3(dnp)$ and $ZrCl_2(dnp)_2$ are fairly good Lewis acids.

Experimental*Materials :*

Zirconium tetrachloride (Fluka) was purified by sublimation in vacuum while 2,4-dinitrophenol, 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl were used after recrystallisation in a suitable solvent and purity was checked by melting points.

Analyses and physical measurements :

Zirconium in the complexes has been determined gravimetrically as ZrO_2 and chlorine by Volhard's method. Carbon and hydrogen microanalyses were performed on Coleman CHN analyzer. The IR spectra were recorded in KBr discs on a Nicolet Avtar model-1000. Molecular weights were determined cryoscopically in nitrobenzene using a Beckmann thermometer while conductance measurements in the same solvent were made on an Elico Conductivity bridge using 10^{-3} M solutions at $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Thermograms were recorded on a Shimadzu simultaneous DT-40, DT-TG thermal analyzer at the heating rate of $20\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$, sample size : 5-10 mg, reference : Al_2O_3 ,

thermocouple : Pt/Pt-Rh 10%.

Preparation of $ZrCl_{4-n}(dnp)_n$:

Compounds of composition $ZrCl_3(dnp)$ and $ZrCl_2(dnp)_2$ were prepared by the reaction of zirconium tetrachloride taken as suspension (4.49 g, 0.019 mol) with equimolar and bimolar amounts of 2,4-dinitrophenol (3.54 g, 0.019 mol and 7.08 g, 0.038 mol) respectively dissolved separately in 50 ml of hot toluene. Immediate evolution of hydrogen chloride gas and change in colour of the solution occurred on mixing. The resulting solution was refluxed till the evolution of hydrogen chloride gas ceased. The compounds from the solutions separated out as fine coloured solids, filtered under anhydrous conditions, washed with ether and finally dried under vacuum.

Preparation of addition compounds of $ZrCl_3(dnp)$ and $ZrCl_2(dnp)_2$ with nitrogen bases : For the preparation of addition compounds of $ZrCl_3(dnp)$ and $ZrCl_2(dnp)_2$, a known weight of the parent compound in toluene (40 ml) was reacted with an equimolar amount of 1,10-phenanthroline, 2,2'-bipyridyl dissolved separately in the same solvent (40 ml) with continuous stirring. A significant change in the colour of the solutions accompanied by the dissolution of the parent compound and slight evolution of heat was observed. After stirring the solution overnight, solid compounds were obtained by the addition of petroleum ether, which were separated by filtration and finally dried under vacuum.

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